

Developing Tools and FAIR Principles for the MetBase Database

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Abstract

MetBase is the largest meteorite database for chemical and isotopic data which can be accessed and visualised through a web-application. MetBase has been founded more than 25 years ago and does not follow FAIR principles, while its accompanying web-app requires a significant technical and design update to become much more versatile. The database will be made FAIR, in particular to become interoperable with a new planetary materials database (Astromat), as well as the globally largest geochemical databases such as EarthChem and GEOROC, and the web-app will receive an entirely new and modular, technical foundation. MetBase will soon be successfully merged with the NASA supported Astromat database, and together with now other databases be accessible through the entirely new Data-Access Visualiser web-app. The new EPMA Data Tools make raw data from instruments FAIR by using the Kadi4Mat electronic lab notebook and a web-app to automatically post-process the raw data before these can be accessed by researchers. The community highly profits from now having only one central meteorite database, access this together with other databases through a technically advanced web-app and have a solution for how instrument data can be easily made FAIR by automatically following community recommended standards and best practises. The two new apps were built and designed particularly to be expandable with new functionalities and transferable to other science domains. Communities around such apps could drive adoption through e.g., hackathons which are attractive and effective low-cost events.

I. Introduction

MetBase is a meteorite database that stores chemical and isotopic compositions, as well as physical properties of meteorites and their components. The database can be accessed via a web-application with a graphical user interface (GUI) on metbase.org. MetBase has been established more than 25 years ago and until recently was the only available, large-scale resource for such data. It is a well-known and -used database within the cosmochemistry community.

Only recently, NASA decided to also set-up a database for Astromaterials, called Astromat. A prime motivation of this new database was to have this for (i) the lunar rocks returned by the Apollo missions and (ii) the returned samples from asteroids such as the Osiris-Rex mission, or future sample return mission from other planetary bodies, including Mars.

MetBase and Astromat are based on two completely different technical foundations and database schemata. The challenge was to align both databases to make them fully interoperable. One significant benefit of this approach was that EarthChem, likely the globally largest holder of geochemical data, has the same database schema as Astromat, which would at the same time make MetBase interoperable with also EarthChem. And as GEOROC, another, and one of the largest maybe 2-3 geochemical databases worldwide was also in the process of aligning their schema with EarthChem, this would at the same time make MetBase fully interoperable with GEOROC, which means that in the end all these large geo- and cosmochemical databases would be fully interoperable (Hezel+, 2021).

Once this was achieved, the existing metbase web-app was to be transferred to an entirely new technical foundation and extended to (i) allow the access and visualisation of additional databases in a single GUI, and (ii) allow for entirely new functionalities and, importantly, make the web-app easily extendable (Hezel+, 2021).

To align MetBase with Astromaterials, we employed a software engineer, who was already familiar with MetBase, to both (i) align the MetBase database schema with the Astromat database schema, and (ii) support the development of the new web-app, we provisionally called Data Access-Visualiser.

A largely underestimated bottleneck when working with databases is data entry, i.e., the transfer of data from the researcher into a database. To solve this bottleneck, we conducted an extensive side project using electron microprobe data (EPMA). The idea was not to directly provide the researcher with the raw data from the EPMA, but to first store the data in an online electronic lab notebook (ELN), which is accessed from a newly build web-app. This web-app would pre-process the data from the ELN record in a way that makes it (i) ready for incorporation in a database and (ii) at the same time much more manageable for the e.g., researcher or student. This new web-app is currently called EPMA Data Tools.

Finally, a number of smaller student projects contributed additional elements to the project, such as a mapping tool, visualisation tools, or a standards database that is helpful for the electron microprobe workflow. These will not be described in detail.

II. Results

a) Implemented Solution

It became clear during the project that a more sensible solution would be to not only align the database schemata of MetBase and Astromat, but to merge both databases into one (Lehnert & Hezel, 2022a,b). Hence, the solution was to fully integrate MetBase into Astromat. Thereby, Astromat partly extended its vocabularies and schema to accommodate new metadata from MetBase. Numerous meetings and discussions were required to achieve this goal, and while it is close to being finished, some last touches are still required. Once all is finalised, a paper is planned to describe the entire process as well as lessons learned.

The technical foundation for the renewed MetBase web-app – now Data-Access Visualiser – has been built, as well as the first technical elements for data access and visualisation. It is now possible to access multiple databases at the same time and visualise these in the same plot or data table. Individual data sets can be produced and (de)selected for display, including own data directly uploaded to the app. (Fig. 1), (Hezel+, 2023).

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Data Access-Visualiser web-app to access and visualise data from various databases.

The EPMA Data Tools use the Kadi4Mat ELN to store the EPMA data, and its Python API (Application Programming Interface) for the actual web-app (Fig. 2). A total of 4 individual files from the EPMA need to be uploaded into one Kadi4Mat record. From these a single method file as well as data file is produced within EPMA Data Tools. The method file essentially stores all relevant metadata of the measurement campaign. A standardised written text is automatically generated from the method data, which can directly be copied and pasted in the 'Methods' section of a publication. A filter tool allows to remove data with e.g., too low or too high totals. All tables are interactive and can be sorted by e.g., an element concentration, or a sample name. Currently, a tool to automatically calculate mineral formulas from the data is implemented, which will be followed by visualisation tools in standard geochemical plots (Hochstein + Hezel, 2023).

Figure 2: Landing page of the EPMA Data Tools web-app.

b) Data and Software availability

Both web-apps are coded with Python and deployed using Streamlit, which in combination allows simple expandability of the apps. Everything will be stored under the MIT license in the public GitHub repository of the Institut für Geowissenschaften at the Goethe Universität Frankfurt.

Tutorials and all relevant links to the web apps, GitHub repositories, as well as documentations for both apps will be available once these are released on geoplatform.de, which has recently been built using Quarto.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

MetBase will soon be entirely interoperable with the major global geochemical databases, as it will be an integral part of Astromat, which is directly associated with EarthChem. By this, MetBase will also be fully reusable – i.e., the data will follow common standards, thereby complying with the arguably two most difficult to fulfil letters in FAIR: I & R.

The new Data-Access Visualiser web-app has an entirely new technical foundation and concept. Accessing the data is separated from manipulating the data. The idea behind this is that a user can first select and package the data from various data sources into individual datasets. This is already a useful change and innovation. These datasets are stored in the cache of a user's computer. The second part of the programme is then manipulating the data from the datasets. For this second part of the programme the previously defined datasets are accessed. This separation allows to easily extend the manipulation part of the programme with new visualisation or even modelling tools. These can be programmed independently from how data are accessed, as these only need to use the user packaged datasets (Fig. 2). At the same time new data sources can be added to the first part of the programme, which can also be developed independently from the data manipulation part. Finally, MetBase now lives in a highly sustainable, NASA supported database.

The EPMA Data Tools is based on the new idea that data are first transferred to an ELN, from where these are accessed by a user. This circumvention of the user allows to first process the raw instrument into common standards, metadata, vocabularies, and best practises, so these become immediately ready to be included in respective, domain specific databases.

We aim to comply with suggested FAIR@RS (Barker+, 2022) principles to make the developed software as sustainable as possible. Deploying the apps as openly available online tools makes complies with the Open Science idea.

III. Challenges and Gaps

It was initially planned to align MetBase with GEOROC. This goal was fully achieved – however by a different path than initially anticipated (cf. above). The new Data-Access Visualiser is on a good path, although not yet ready. This was not necessarily expected, as the prime goal was to layout the new technical foundation, which has been achieved.

Mapping one database onto another is a major task, and by far not a simple, straightforward coding to map some vocabularies and metadata onto another. This is particularly true for legacy databases such as MetBase, which could not follow existing vocabularies or metadata when it was established. It is critical that all newly produced data follow best practises, which are rooted in community accepted standards (cf. Klöcking+, 2023). A solution to achieve this complicated goal could be the use of ELNs in the way described above.

It is finally critical that RSE and digital skills are more widely accepted and adopted and conveyed to students from early on.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth (min. ½ page)

The community will now be able to access MetBase and Astromat from single interfaces. Astromat has its own access point to retrieve data, and our newly developed web-app will allow to access all meteorite data, and plot or use these together with other database data. This eases the search and use of meteorite and other planetary data, which are now stored in a single place. As we decided along the way to fully merge MetBase with Astromat, MetBase became sustainable. The Data-Access Visualiser app is potentially useful for the entire cosmochemistry and geochemistry community. In particular, as it is extendable by anyone with some Python knowledge. The app now consists of two technically different parts, which, however, to the user appears as one. The first part accesses the various data sources using API requests and maps the retrieved data formats into single datasets. This might be a blueprint for similar tools from other science domains. In fact, this idea of splitting the data access and manipulation part might be a sensible approach for such tools from other domains.

The EPMA Data Tools show how data are stored securely, before a researcher access these. Of course, a researcher must not use the pre-processed data from the web-app. The raw data are always also accessible directly from the Kadi4Mat ELN. The goal, however, is to provide a richer and more useful interface that at the same time follows community accepted best

practises for data management. This EPMA Data Tools is the test run for such a workflow at our institute, and if successful, could be rolled out to other laboratories.

Once the EPMA portal is fully working – i.e., within the next weeks – we will plan to publish this new workflow in an appropriate journal.

First results were already published in abstracts and presented in various conferences, among these the Annual Meeting of the Meteoritical Society, as well as the the EGU and Goldschmidt conferences. The apps are included in the geoplatform.de webpage, to be findable in one place. Finally, results might find their way in the planned distribution platform of the currently forming global OneGeochemistry initiative (Prent+, 2023), and will be made available in NFDI4Earth Living Handbook articles.

V. Future Directions (min. ½ page)

After merging MetBase with Astromat, the future direction and challenge remains data input from the community with following community standards and recommendations when publishing data. A number of cultural changes are likely required to achieve this: (i) teaching students from the start how FAIR data implementation works, (ii) the initial step from data acquisition to a FAIR dataset must become simple through digital tools such as electronic lab books with automated post-processing tools, (iii) publications and funders need to only accept datasets that follow community recommended standards, or datasets that have been accepted by an accredited, domain specific data repository or database.

The Data Access Visualiser as well as the EPMA Data Tools codes are available on GitHub. Anyone is invited to view the code and make merge request for additional functionalities. Creating communities around these or similar codes could be a way forward to build community driven, tailored research software to satisfy the needs for working with data as well as producing FAIR datasets.

Such research software requires continuous maintenance, adjustments and development. Annual hackathons of 3-5 days with e.g., 5-20 participants could be attractive events to interest students and the community to progress and implement such research software. Such comparatively low-cost meetings with support for in particular students have the potential to significantly improve existing software to the next level and accelerate the adoption and acceptance of the developed research software. Funding for such hackathons could be provided by the NFDI4Earth or DFG. Funding for research software around data in general requires complementary broad funding schemes and programmes from e.g., the DFG.

Both, the Data-Access Visualiser and the EPMA Data Tools will be further developed at the Institut für Geowissenschaften at the Goethe Universität Frankfurt.

References

Barker M., Hong N. P. C., Katz D. S., Lamprecht A.-L., Martinez-Ortiz C., Psomopoulos F., Harrow J., Castro L. J., Gruenpeter M., Martinez P. A. and Honeyman T. (2022) Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Sci Data* 9, 622.

- Hezel DC, Elangovan P, Lehnert KA, Klöcking M, Sturm A, Marschall H (2023) A single web-interface to access, visualise and model data from multiple geo- and cosmochemical databases. Goldschmidt Conference 2023.
- Hochstein M, Hezel DC (2023) Post-Processing and making electron microprobe data FAIR with a new, open web-interface that is connected to an electronic lab notebook. Goldschmidt Conference 2023.
- Klöcking M, Wyborn L, Lehnert KA, Ware B, Prent AM, Profeta L, Kohlmann F, Noble W, Bruno I, Lambart S, Ananuer H, Barber ND, Becker H, Brodbeck M, Deng H, Deng K, Elger K, Franco GdS, Gao Y, Ghasera KM, Hezel DC, Huang J, Kerswell B, Koch H, Lanati AW, Maat Gt, Martínez-Villegas N, Yobo LN, Redaa A, Schäfer W, Swing MR, Taylor RJM, Traun MK, Whelan J, Zhou T (2023) Community recommendations for geochemical data, services and analytical capabilities in the 21st century. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* (in press).
- Prent AM, Hezel DC, Klöcking M, Wyborn L, Farrington R, Lehnert K, Elger K, Profeta L (2023) Innovating and networking global geochemical data resources through OneGeochemistry. *Elements* (in press)
- Hezel DC, Lehnert KA (2022a) Closing the gap between related databases: MetBase and the Astromaterials Data System (Astromat) plan for a common future. id.EGU22-13457.
- Hezel DC, Lehnert KA (2022b) The Future of Cosmochemical Databases: MetBase and the Astromaterials Data System (ASTROMAT) Started a Common Future. 85th Annual Meeting of The Meteoritical Society LPI Contribution No. 2695.
- Hezel, DC, Marschall, HR, Klöcking M, Lehnert KA (2021) Upgrading MetBase to Becoming Fully FAIR and an Integral Part of International Initiatives. Astromaterials Data Management in the Era of Sample-Return Missions Community Workshop, LPI Contribution No. 2654.